

Ontolex-Lemon in Wikidata and other Wikibase instances

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Abstract

This paper provides insight into how the core elements of the Ontolex-Lemon model are integrated in the *Wikibase Ontology*, the data model fundamental to any instance of the Wikibase software. This includes *Wikidata lexemes*, which today is probably the largest Ontolex-Lemon use case, a dataset collaboratively built by the community of Wikidata users. We describe how lexical entries are modeled on a Wikibase, including the linguistic description of lexemes, the linking of lexical entries, lexical senses and lexical forms across resources, and links across the domain of lexemes and the ontological part of a Wikibase knowledge graph. Our aim is to present Wikibase as a solution for storing and collaboratively editing lexical data following Semantic Web standards, and to identify relevant research questions to be addressed in future work.

1 Introduction

Wikibase,¹ a set of extensions to MediaWiki², is a software solution for storing, collaboratively editing and exhibiting structured data on the web, in the shape of a knowledge graph. The software is used, first and foremost, by Wikidata (Vrandečić and Krötzsch, 2014; Erxleben et al., 2014).³ Many other instances of the software have emerged since the software packages (and hosting solutions) are freely available.⁴ The types of entities described in a Wikibase include *items*, which represent all kinds of real-world objects and ontological concepts, and *lexemes*, describing words. As it will be explained in section 2.1, in a Wikibase, lexemes are described following the core of the Ontolex-Lemon model (McCrae et al., 2017), and so they are on Wikidata, which is today probably the largest open and

collaboratively editable Ontolex-Lemon use case. By May 2025, Wikidata described 1.42 Million lexical entries in 1,379 different languages, which compared to earlier figures (Nielsen, 2020) means an exponential growth. German, Russian, Danish, Estonian, English and Malayalam are, in this order, the languages with the most described lexemes. The potential uses of the linguistic descriptions contained in this growing resource, which we present in more detail in section 2.2, are manifold.

Section 2.3 is devoted to Wikibase as a linking hub for descriptions of lexical *entries*, *senses* and *forms* across different resources; cross-resource links are encoded as *external ID* properties.⁵ External identifiers do not only constitute hyperlinks for a user to jump between the resources presented in different web portals, but also enable SPARQL federation,⁶ that is, a Wikibase's content may be integrated also with the lexical and ontological content of any other Wikibase, including Wikidata, or an RDF database of other kind.⁷ In this regard, it is important to point out how RDF is used on a Wikibase, which will be explained in section 2.4. Related to this, an important and distinguishing feature of Wikibase is its multi-layer integration of lexical and ontological entities inside the same database, which will be discussed in detail in section 2.5.

While the lexemes collection on Wikidata is open for continued enrichment, some use cases may require a separate Wikibase instance, in a first phase of a contribution project, or even for a whole project lifetime: A language may be already described on Wikidata, so that any addition would involve lexeme, sense and form disambiguation

¹See <https://wikiba.se>.

²See <https://mediawiki.org>.

³See <https://www.wikidata.org>.

⁴See <https://wikiba.se/showcase/> and <https://wikibase.world>, a catalogue of Wikibase instances.

⁵See https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:External_identifiers.

⁶See <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-federated-query/>.

⁷See <https://www.mediawiki.org/wiki/Wikibase/Federation>.

and deduplication tasks, which when working on an own instance could be left to the final phase of a project. Also, a dataset to be curated may be regarded too noisy (e. g. in a legacy dictionary digitisation project), or too esoteric (e. g. when dealing with dialectal or historical language data) to be included in Wikidata without previously ensuring relevance and quality. In addition, to work on an own Wikibase instance means freedom in data modeling and community management. Licensing might also be an issue, since Wikidata content is obligatorily licensed according to CC0. Exploring these potentials, we briefly discuss the Wikibase ecosystem for lexeme descriptions in section 2.6.

In the closing section 3, we provide an outlook for open research questions to be worked on, focusing on the relation between the fine-grained modeling proposals made by the Ontolex Community, on the one hand, and the conventions emerging in the community working on Wikidata lexemes, on the other.

2 Ontolex-Lemon on Wikibase

2.1 Lemon core classes

The core of Ontolex-Lemon,⁸ that is, the classes `ontolex:LexicalEntry`, `ontolex:LexicalSense`, and `ontolex:Form`, is reused in the Wikibase Ontology,⁹ the backbone model of any Wikibase instance.

Wikibase treats the lexical entry, with its own numeral identifier preceded by letter L, as primary entity describing a *lexeme*, with forms and senses as sub-entities, and presents the instances of those three Ontolex-Lemon core classes together on one editable lexeme page.¹⁰ This structure is pre-set in the data model fundamental to any Wikibase instance and cannot be modified by the user, and the same is true for a small number of properties to be attached to the three core classes, listed in table 1; the three obligatory properties describing a lexical *entry* must have a value, a *sense* must have a *gloss* (a short sense-disambiguating text, represented in RDF using `skos:definition`), and a *form* must have a representation (a value for `ontolex:representation`).¹¹

⁸For the original Lexical Model for Ontologies, see <https://lemon-model.net/>.

⁹See <https://wikiba.se/ontology/>.

¹⁰See <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Lexeme:L1> for the lexeme page describing lexeme `wd:L1`.

¹¹Although `ontolex:writtenRep` would be the best match here, the Wikibase Ontology uses `ontolex:representation`;

ontolex:LexicalEntry
<code>wikibase:lemma</code>
<code>wikibase:lexicalCategory</code>
<code>dct:language</code>
<code>ontolex:sense</code>
<code>ontolex:lexicalForm</code>
ontolex:LexicalSense
<code>skos:definition</code>
ontolex:Form
<code>wikibase:grammaticalFeature</code>
<code>ontolex:representation</code>

Table 1: Obligatory basic classes and properties in their domain for describing lexemes in Wikibase

In detail, this obligatory structure entails the following restrictions:

- A lexical *entry* must point to exactly one item in the same Wikibase as value for *lexical category*.
- A lexical *entry* must point to exactly one item in the same Wikibase as value for its *language*.
- A lexical *entry* must have at least one *lemma*. Several lemmata can co-exist for the same *entry* for covering different spelling variants (e. g. British and American English).¹² In the RDF representation, lexeme lemmata appear attached to the entry using a property named `wikibase:lemma`. Lemmata are indexed for the MediaWiki text search index,¹³ so that a user can search for lexemes, manually in the interface, or via API.
- A lexical *sense* must have at least one *sense gloss*, in any language, i. e. not necessarily or not only in the language associated to the *entry*. Purpose of the gloss is to provide the information necessary to discriminate word senses.
- A *form* must have at least one *written representation*. Alike different values for *lemma*

in Ontolex-Lemon, the former is defined as subproperty of the latter.

¹²See an example at <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Lexeme:L1347>, where the English *color/colour* is described, an example for an entry with lemmata in distinct scripts at <https://kurdi.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Lexeme:L3447>.

¹³See <https://www.mediawiki.org/wiki/Elasticsearch>.

on entry level, form representations in several spelling variants can be attached to the same *form* entity. A written representation in most cases will be a string as found in text of that language, but written representations also include code transcriptions, such as those describing sign language forms.¹⁴ To describe a form without providing any type of written representation is not foreseen.

- A *form* can have zero or more items in the same Wikibase as values for *grammatical feature*.

Lemmata, *sense* glosses (*skos:definition*), and also *form* representations (*ontolex:representation*) are associated to a language code. The available codes are the same that are available throughout the mediaWiki instance, e. g. for labels, descriptions, and *monolingualtext* strings.¹⁵

Figure 1: The Wikibase lexeme, as illustrated in the Wikibase documentation

These restrictions guarantee interoperability on a basic level. Beyond that, any additional relation involving *entry*, *sense* or *form* objects is not

¹⁴For an example, see [wd:L991786-F1](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/L991786-F1).

¹⁵See https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Monolingual_text_languages, and for a list of all codes implemented in a Wikibase instance, e. g. <https://www.wikidata.org/w/api.php?action=query&meta=wbcontentlanguages>.

predefined and can be modeled according to the use case using self-defined properties in Wikibase *statements*,¹⁶ as illustrated in Fig. 1.¹⁷ The RDF classes and properties mentioned above are part of the Wikibase Ontology, that is, they are used in the RDF representation of an entity (an *item*, a *lexeme*, a *property*), and accordingly, they appear in RDF entity data dumps.¹⁸ In opposition to that, all other relations added to *lexeme*, *sense* or *form* as Wikibase *statements* (see section 2.4) always involve a property defined in the namespace of the Wikibase instance itself, identified by a number preceded by the letter P, and that has a range restricted to one Wikibase datatype.¹⁹

2.2 Wikidata lexemes

Wikidata lexemes is an open and editable collection, where everybody is invited to collaborate. A documentation of the data model based on the three Ontolex-Lemon core classes is given on the Wikidata documentation pages.²⁰ Concerning advanced modeling questions, contributors get support from each other.²¹ A core group of more experienced and active users provides advice to newcomers and occasional contributors, also through dedicated outreach events.²² A manually curated list of lexical entries provides examples in several languages of good and complete modeling practice.²³

Instead of following prescribed models concerning morphology, etymology, multilingual equivalents, etc., on Wikidata, a bottom-up grown set of properties is used for describing entries, senses, and forms; see table 2 for the ten most frequent properties for each of the classes, pointing to other

¹⁶See <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Statements>.

¹⁷The picture is used at https://www.mediawiki.org/wiki/Extension:WikibaseLexeme/Data_Model.

¹⁸In Turtle serialization, see, for example, <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Special:EntityData/L1347.ttl>.

¹⁹See https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Data_type.

²⁰See https://www.mediawiki.org/wiki/Extension:WikibaseLexeme/Data_Model.

²¹Discussions take place on-wiki (see https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata_talk:Lexicographical_data) and in a dedicated channel on the *Telegram* platform.

²²The pages dedicated to the 2021 and the 2024 *Lexicodays* provide video recordings, presentation slides and links to other pages containing lexicographical guidelines and descriptions of tools related to Wikidata lexemes, see https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Events/Lexicodays_2024 and https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Events/30_lexic-o-days_2021

²³See https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Showcase_lexemes.

entities on Wikidata, or to a data value (in table 2, excluding *external id* properties). Without going into much detail, we point out some of them; in some cases, the modeling is unambiguous (and straightforwardly alignable to Ontolex), and sometimes alternative modeling approaches coexist:

- As it will be explained in section 2.5, **translation equivalence** is expressed using [wd:P5972](#), a property set (in both directions) directly between senses; the property used in Ontolex-Lemon for this purpose is [vartrans:translation](#). In May 2025, Wikidata contained 119,847 translation links between senses of different languages.
- For representing **etymology**, a lexeme is linked directly to the lexical entry describing the etymon using [wd:P5191](#).²⁴ In May 2025, Wikidata contained 40,540 etymology links from lexeme to lexeme.
- For representing **decomposition**, [wd:P5238](#), the *combines lexeme* property links a compound or multiword entry to its constituents, in the same way [decomp:subterm](#) is used according to Ontolex.²⁵ This property is used in May 2025 207,799 times.
- **Pronunciation** is described in multiple ways, but always associated to *forms*; the value of a general *pronunciation* property [wd:P7243](#) is in general identical to the form representation, but may include stress indicators and other diacritics, e. g. to indicate vowel length. It is recommended that pronunciation audio files and/or IPA transcriptions are attached as *qualifiers* to the pronunciation claim, but audio files can also be directly attached to *form*.²⁶ Today, 74% of 252,652 pronunciation audio files are linked directly to a *form*. Only audio files hosted on Wikimedia Commons can be used.²⁷
- As seen in table 2, properties devoted to certain **transcription** and **transliteration** sys-

tems exist; each of them is, like all Wikidata properties, described through its entity data, and on an own discussion page.²⁸ In parallel, a general property *transliteration or transcription* ([wd:P2440](#)) can be used, and its value qualified using the property *determination method or standard* ([wd:P459](#)). The former, defined as subproperties of [wd:P2440](#), are heavily used on Wikidata in general,²⁹ but in only about 1.2% of its use cases (i. e., not more than 3,808), that property is attached to *forms*,³⁰ on which the general property is used around ten times more often: The 70,165 uses of [wd:P2440](#), with a [wd:P459](#) qualifier pointing to the transliteration system, are almost half-divided between *items* and *forms*.³¹

- **Usage examples** ([wd:P5831](#)) are recommended to be attached to *entry*, and not to *sense*. However, about 7% of the 31,271 usage examples in Wikidata lexemes today remain attached to *sense*; the distribution across languages shows a diverse picture, but a clear preference for *entry* as subject of the property.³² If attached to *entry*, one or more senses can be declared *subject sense* ([wd:P6072](#)); this is done using that property as qualifier in the example statement. The advantage of this modeling, apart from being able to declare a usage example to be pertinent to more than one sense, lies in the ability to have examples attached to the entry also if in the moment of upload and without or before whatever sense disambiguation procedure it is not clear which sense should be marked as *subject sense*, e. g. when dealing with examples stemming from corpora, or if (still) no senses are described for the lexeme: As soon as the correct sense can be determined, the [wd:P5831 claim](#) is enriched with with a [wd:P6072 qualifier](#), without having to delete and re-write the whole *statement* (with its references), and attach it to *sense*. Another strong reason for attaching

²⁴See, for example, <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Lexeme:L630740#P5191>.

²⁵See [wd:L625224](#) for the German phrase "frohes neues Jahr".

²⁶For an example, see [wd:L3338-F2](#). *Qualifiers* as part of a *statement* are explained in section 2.4

²⁷The property is of datatype *Commons Media File*, see https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Data_type#commonsMedia.

²⁸For example, about the property [wd:P5825 ISO 15919 transliteration](#), a documentation is available at https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property_talk:P5825, and about [wd:P4187 Tibetan to Latin transliteration](#), https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property_talk:P4187.

²⁹See <https://w.wiki/EBWF>.

³⁰See <https://w.wiki/EBYi>.

³¹See <https://w.wiki/EBZ2> for usage counts according to the different transliteration systems.

³²See <https://w.wiki/ECBm> for the use of this property across languages.

usage examples to entry is to enable their annotation with a subject *form*, i. e. the word form appearing in the example.³³ In addition, having examples at both levels complicates their retrieval in queries.

The Wikidata lexemes collection is quantitatively described on dedicated pages,³⁴ and it can be explored using the *Ordia* tool (Nielsen, 2019),³⁵ which generates dictionary-like exhibitions of lexical data; it also features a tool to look up Wikidata *forms* matching to tokens in text. *Ordia* also provides statistics on the Wikidata lexeme collection, such as, for example, lists of the most frequently used properties in the domains of *entry* (a. k. a. *lexeme*), *sense* and *form*.³⁶ The *Synia* tool also shows statistics on lexemes, e. g. counts of values for [wd:P6191](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Lexicographical_data/Statistics) *language style* in different languages.³⁷

Table 3 lists overall counts for the ten languages with best absolute coverage at the three levels.³⁸ Asking for relative coverages, without data about the total amount of corpus lemmata, corpus types, and dictionary senses in a language, we might ask for a relation between the coverage on Wikidata and the number of speakers of a language. A query like that (taking into account languages with more than 100,000 speakers) results in a different ranking, with Estonian, Breton, Basque and Danish leading lexemes,³⁹ and Basque, Breton, Dagbani and Norwegian Bokmål as top four languages for senses.⁴⁰

Apart from those already mentioned, a range of tools⁴¹ has emerged around Wikidata lexemes, designed to help creating entries and append senses,⁴²

³³See, for example, the usage examples for [wd:L87](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/L87).

³⁴See https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Lexicographical_data/Statistics

³⁵Accessible at <https://ordia.toolforge.org/>.

³⁶Accessible at <https://ordia.toolforge.org/property/>. Wikidata SPARQL queries as used in *Ordia* can be modified for custom searches, e. g. for listing the property statistics for a single language, as in the following queries derived from those in *Ordia*: *entry*, <https://w.wiki/E4pg>, *sense*, <https://w.wiki/E4pw>, *Form*, [https://w.wiki/E4p\\$](https://w.wiki/E4p$); note the filter for *external id* properties.

³⁷See <https://synia.toolforge.org/#languagestyle>.

³⁸See up-to-date statistics at <https://w.wiki/ECLq> for *lexeme*, at <https://w.wiki/EDkc> for *sense*, and at <https://w.wiki/EDjh> for *form*.

³⁹See <https://w.wiki/EDna>.

⁴⁰See <https://w.wiki/EDnQ>.

⁴¹See also https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Tools/Lexicographical_data.

⁴²For a lexeme creation UI, see <https://hangor.toolforge.org>; for python, in addition to the gen-

LexicalEntry	
wd:P5185	<i>grammatical gender</i>
wd:P5911	<i>paradigm class</i>
wd:P5238	<i>combines lexeme</i>
wd:P31	<i>instance of</i>
wd:P5187	<i>word stem</i>
wd:P1552	<i>has characteristic</i>
wd:P5402	<i>homograph lexeme</i>
wd:P2348	<i>time period</i>
wd:P5191	<i>derived from lexeme</i>
wd:P5186	<i>conjugation class</i>
wd:P5831	<i>usage example</i>
wd:P7486	<i>grammatical aspect</i>
LexicalSense	
wd:P5137	<i>item for this sense</i>
wd:P5972	<i>translation</i>
wd:P5973	<i>synonym</i>
wd:P1343	<i>described by source</i>
wd:P18	<i>image</i>
wd:P9488	<i>field of usage</i>
wd:P6191	<i>language style</i>
wd:P8394	<i>gloss quote</i>
wd:P9970	<i>predicate for</i>
wd:P6271	<i>demonym of</i>
wd:P6084	<i>location of sense usage</i>
wd:P10339	<i>semantic gender</i>
Form	
wd:P7243	<i>pronunciation</i>
wd:P898	<i>IPA transcription</i>
wd:P443	<i>pronunciation audio</i>
wd:P5279	<i>hyphenation</i>
wd:P5825	<i>ISO 15919 transliteration</i>
wd:P8881	<i>ITRANS (Indic scripts)</i>
wd:P8530	<i>alternative form</i>
wd:P5276	<i>Slavistic Phonetic Alphabet transcr.</i>
wd:P10822	<i>homophone form</i>
wd:P1721	<i>Hanyu Pinyin transliteration</i>
wd:P11950	<i>appears before phonological feature</i>
wd:P11951	<i>appears after phonological feature</i>

Table 2: The 12 most frequently used properties describing Wikidata lexemes, senses and forms (May 2025)

for linking senses to ontological references,⁴³ for creating forms collections through templates,⁴⁴ searching for usage examples and adding them to

eral *wikibaseintegrator* library (<https://github.com/LeMyst/WikibaseIntegrator>), specially for lexemes, *tfsi* (<https://gitlab.wikimedia.org/toolforge-repos/twofivesixlex>).

⁴³See <https://lexica-tool.toolforge.org/>.

⁴⁴See https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Wikidata_Lexeme_Forms.

LexicalEntry	language	LexicalSense	language	Form	language
1,422,331	all Wikidata	585,893	all Wikidata	14,396,207	all Wikidata
239,465	German	48,308	Bokmål	2,802,106	Estonian
102,150	Russian	41,973	English	1,257,083	Basque
96,753	Danish	30,756	Basque	1,246,745	Russian
83,218	Estonian	29,790	Nynorsk	1,199,194	Latin
68,758	English	24,127	Czech	871,813	Czech
67,367	Malayalam	24,055	Swedish	753,118	Malayalam
64,445	Italian	22,000	Italian	692,671	Spanish
63,128	Spanish	21,036	Japanese	641,454	Danish
56,296	Latin	20,484	Persian	571,091	German
48,214	Swedish	18,851	Egyptian	522,107	Italian

Table 3: Absolute coverage of some languages in Wikidata lexemes (May 2025)

entries,⁴⁵ for massively recording pronunciation audios,⁴⁶ or for graph visualisations of lexical relations.⁴⁷

One goal of the Wikidata lexemes collection is to enable natural language generation for drafting Wikipedia article text from abstract knowledge representations (Vrandečić, 2021; Morshed, 2024),⁴⁸ and another possible application is corpus annotation (Lindemann and Alonso, 2024); all these depend on the degree the lexemes, senses and forms in the collection cover the languages to process.

2.3 Wikibase lexemes as linking hub: The case of Wikidata

In addition to these and other properties for the linguistic description of the lexeme, Wikibase lexical entries contain pointers to external resources encoded as *external id* properties. These lead a human user to an entry or sense description in a dictionary web portal. In some cases, federated database queries can access content in several graph databases at a time using such external ID. For example, a query can involve Wikidata and the LiLa Latin Knowledge Base (Passarotti and Mambrini, 2022),⁴⁹ exploiting the LiLa URI attached to Wikidata Latin lexemes, and calling the LiLa SPARQL endpoint from within the Wikidata Query Service, or vice versa.

⁴⁵The *Luthor* tool uses Wikisource content as corpus, see <https://luthor.toolforge.org/>.

⁴⁶See <https://lingualibre.org/>.

⁴⁷For an example, an etymological network, see <https://lucaswerkmeister.github.io/wikidata-lexeme-graph-builder/?subjects=L18495&predicates=P5191>.

⁴⁸See https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Abstract_Wikipedia.

⁴⁹See <https://lila-erc.eu/>; the LiLa ID property is `wd:P11033`.

Wikidata lexemes, on *entry* level, by May 2025 count 2.3 Million *external id* statements. Table 4 shows usage counts for the most frequent 20 properties.⁵⁰ As for *sense*, all lexical resources aligned to Wikidata on sense level today still lack significant coverage,⁵¹ although we point out the fact that e. g. English Wordnet synset identifiers are aligned to Wikidata *items* (McCrae and Cillessen, 2021), which, as explained, are referenced by a significant number or senses. An alignment of *forms* to external resources such as corpus-based form repositories is at large still not present, although it would be interesting, for instance in rich-morphology languages, where the morphologically possible forms outnumber the forms that are actually attested in corpora, so that forms attestation is very valuable information, with a similar value lemma attestation has in languages with a comparably reduced number of different inflected forms, like English.

2.4 Reification in Wikibase

Wikibase *statements* include by default a mechanism for further describing the main *claim* of a statement using *qualifiers*, *ranks*, and *references*. A graphical model of a Wikibase statement is given in figure 2, where "entity" represents an *item*, *lexeme*, *sense*, *form*, or *property* node, each of which has its own URI in the main entity namespace of the Wikibase instance,⁵² and where the blue-colored "value" nodes, depending on the property datatype, represent entities of the same Wikibase, or data val-

⁵⁰For up-to-date counts, see <https://w.wiki/E9j3>.

⁵¹An example for one of the most used external identifiers is *DWDS sense ID*, see https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property_talk:P12550.

⁵²On Wikidata, e. g. `wd:Q1` for an item, `wd:L1` for a lexeme, `wd:L1-S1` for a sense, `wd:L1-F1` for a form, and `wd:P31` for a property.

Count	Property	Property label (en)	Lang. (ISO-639-1)
231,859	wd:P9940	<i>DWDS-Lemma-Identifikator</i>	de
153,322	wd:P8376	<i>Duden-Lexem-Identifikator</i>	de
139,067	wd:P11519	<i>elexiko ID</i>	de
122,350	wd:P11138	<i>Sõnaveeb entry ID</i>	(45 lang.)
84,951	wd:P9947	<i>WDG-Lemma-Identifikator</i>	de
66,512	wd:P13258	<i>Presisov večjezični slovar ID</i>	fr de en sq sh
65,599	wd:P9529	<i>Den Danske Ordbog article ID</i>	da
61,333	wd:P5912	<i>Oqaasileriffik online dictionary ID</i>	da en kl nb
54,755	wd:P12630	<i>Aragonario ID (6th version)</i>	es an
51,566	wd:P11033	<i>LiLa Linking Latin URI</i>	la
49,987	wd:P9385	<i>DWB Lemma ID</i>	de
45,751	wd:P5275	<i>OED Online ID</i>	en
39,052	wd:P9962	<i>Ordbog over det danske sprog ID</i>	da
37,925	wd:P12420	<i>Il Nuovo De Mauro ID</i>	it
37,137	wd:P10042	<i>Bokmålsordboka-ID</i>	nb nn
36,535	wd:P11838	<i>Svenska Akademiens ordlista ID</i>	sv
35,124	wd:P9387	<i>GWB Lemma ID</i>	de
31,014	wd:P12690	<i>New Oxford American Dictionary ID</i>	en
29,803	wd:P11319	<i>Little Academic Dictionary ID</i>	ru
29,316	wd:P12828	<i>DAKA Danish-Greenlandic Dictionary ID</i>	da

Table 4: Most frequently used *external id* properties on Wikidata lexemes, and lexeme languages

Figure 2: Graphical model of a Wikibase Statement

ues, including strings, external identifiers, date objects, globe coordinates, et cetera. Each statement node may be linked to several *qualifier* values, and to several *reference* nodes (in the RDF representation attached to the statement blank node using `prov:wasDerivedFrom`), which make up blocks of references. *Ranks* are used for annotating multiple

statements for the same property with one of the three values *normal*, *preferred*, or *deprecated*.⁵³

In order to keep all data pertaining to the same lexical entry "together", so that it would all get stored in the same entity data JSON blob,⁵⁴ and displayed on the same lexeme entity page, it is convenient to keep the modeling of the linguistic description as shallow as a list of Wikibase *statements*. Unlike in the Ontolex modules, where the linguistic description often involves several reification layers, the model followed in Wikidata, and, for the same reason, in any other Wikibase, will try, wherever possible, to stay with certain reification approaches, which can be combined, but will be limited to the following:

- Using statement *qualifiers*, i. e. semantic triples describing the main *claim* of the statement.
- Using *references* for provenance annotations.
- Using subproperties such as `wd:P1721`

⁵³See <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Ranking>.

⁵⁴At <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Special:EntityData/L1.json>, the entity data JSON for `wd:L1` as stored in the database, and from which the entity page display is generated, can be obtained.

Hanyu Pinyin transliteration, subproperty of [wd:P2440 transliteration or transcription](#).

If we compare, for example, how a translation relation between two senses can be further described, according to Ontolex this can be modeled introducing a blank node of class `vartrans:Translation` into the dataset (option A), linking that to both *sense* nodes using typed properties (*source* and *target*), and attaching to that node supplemental information about the translation relation (Bosque-Gil et al., 2015). As a shallower alternative (option B), which does not involve any additional blank node in the structure, and consequently allows no additional description of the translation relation, Ontolex uses the `vartrans:translation` property.⁵⁵ The second option is more suitable for a Wikibase, because the additional node in option A, since it does not fit into the Wikibase statement structure, would have to be created as named individual entity, i. e. a Wikibase *item* with its own Q-identifier, its labels to be indexed in the Wikibase ElasticSearch, its class declaration, and descriptions. However, in a Wikibase, option B caters for a description as rich as option A in Ontolex: In the discussed example, the translation relation type, its direction, or any other translation restriction feature can be expressed using a *qualifier* on the translation *claim*. This, in turn, is not possible when using option B in Ontolex, since the semantic triple describing the translation relation there cannot be further described or qualified.

2.5 Lexicon-Ontology interface and multilinguality

According to Ontolex-Lemon, a property named `ontolex:reference` links a lexical sense to an ontological concept (Bosque-Gil et al., 2015). On Wikidata, [wd:P5137 item for this sense](#) has the equivalent function. For example, Wikidata’s lexeme [wd:L3549](#), describing the English noun *foot*, has three senses, each of them pointing to a different conceptual *item* node in the graph, using that property. [wd:L3549-S1](#), the first listed sense, is linked to an item describing a unit of length, while the second sense points to an item describing a furniture part, and the third sense, [wd:L3549-S3](#), glossed as “anatomical structure found in vertebrates”, links to the anatomical entity. Each of the three linked Wikidata *items* is

⁵⁵See examples with figures for both at <https://www.w3.org/2016/05/ontolex/#translation-as-a-relation-between-lexical-senses>.

itself further described, for example, with links to Wikipedia articles in multiple languages (the property used here is `schema:about`), which have a title in that language, and which provide encyclopaedical descriptions of the concept. That means in general terms that Wikibase provides a framework where lexical and ontological (conceptual) descriptions converge, and where text pages (for Wikidata, Wikipedia articles) *about* concepts also have their habitat. Since, in addition, Wikibase items are annotated with multilingual labels (`rdfs:label` and `skos:altLabel`) and descriptions (`schema:description`), the [wd:P5137](#) reference of a lexeme sense into the ontological part of the Wikidata graph already provides three facets of multilinguality: The labels, textual concept descriptions, and entire text pages attached to an ontological item referenced by lexeme senses may cover multiple languages.

Since several languages’ word senses can be linked to the same *item*, [wd:P5137](#) provides translation (and, inside the same language, synonymy) information. In Ontolex, this way of modeling translation relations is referred to as *translation as shared reference*.⁵⁶ As of May 2025, Wikidata contains 227,908 *item for this sense* claims that link senses to items.⁵⁷ Calculating the number of translation links through shared references for every item, that sums 5.23 million translation (and intralingual synonymy) links between lexeme senses, counting the connecting links twice, i. e. as translation link in both directions.⁵⁸ This by far outnumbers [wd:P5972 sense translation](#) relations (see section 2.2), which constitute an alternative without leaving the domain of lexemes, as needed for senses without an ontological reference in Wikidata (most prominently, senses of lexemes with a lexical category other than *noun*). As described above, multilingual sense *glosses* (very short sense descriptions attached using the built-in `skos:definition`) provide another facet of multilingual sense description.

Fig. 3 shows an example for a lexeme’s relations in the graph, including *monolingualtext* values in two languages: the lexical entry describing a German noun *Pferd* (“horse”), linked to entities of dif-

⁵⁶See <https://www.w3.org/2016/05/ontolex/#translation-as-shared-reference>.

⁵⁷See the distribution of *item for this sense* across languages at <https://w.wiki/ECCA>.

⁵⁸See <https://w.wiki/EcDh> for a list of all items linked to from senses, and the corresponding number of translation links (includes intralingual translation, i. e. synonymy).

Figure 3: Wikidata entry `wd:L34708` describing the German lemma *Pferd* and some relations

ferent types: ontological concepts (*items*), other lexical entries (*lexemes*), and lexical senses. Entities of type *item* are used to represent the *language*, which allows querying for lexemes according to language features such as the language family or countries where languages are spoken or native to, to represent the *lexical category*,⁵⁹ and, as explained above, for ontological sense references. *Label*, *definition* and *lemma* values are always strings associated to a language code (figure 3 only shows English and German, while the cited entities on Wikidata cover more languages here).

2.6 Wikibase as an infrastructure for lexical datasets

In terms of the *FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*⁶⁰, a lexical dataset on a Wikibase can safely be called to be state of the art, since permanent URI on the level

⁵⁹On Wikidata, a range of 320 different *items* is used here, some defined as subclasses of others, e. g. `wd:Q1166153 intransitive verb subclass of wd:Q24905 verb`; see <https://w.wiki/ECKP> for use counts.

⁶⁰See <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

of the three Ontolex-Lemon core classes assure *findability*, answering human user calls with the display of an editable entity page, and programmatical calls with machine-readable data in various formats.⁶¹ *Accessibility* is furthermore given through the graphical query service,⁶² and through a SPARQL endpoint. *Interoperability* is sustained by re-using W3C-recommended RDF vocabularies for a set of basic classes and properties defined in the Wikibase Ontology, such as Ontolex-Lemon for lexical data. Finally, *reusability* is ensured by open licenses.⁶³

Wikimedia Deutschland, the WMF chapter responsible for Wikidata, is providing the Wikibase software for self-hosting,⁶⁴ and also provides a

⁶¹Entity data dumps are available in JSON and TTL format.

⁶²For Wikidata, accessible at <https://query.wikidata.org/>.

⁶³Wikidata declares its terms of use at the bottom of every displayed page, and in detail at https://foundation.wikimedia.org/wiki/Policy:Terms_of_Use, and any other Wikibase may contain declarations in a similar form.

⁶⁴See <https://www.mediawiki.org/wiki/Wikibase/Docker>.

hosting cloud.⁶⁵ In community discussions, the vision connected to that embraces an ecosystem of independent but federated Wikibases, with Wikidata as central linking hub.⁶⁶ Regarding several domains of knowledge, this is already becoming reality; also related to lexical data, some projects have been able to showcase the potential this infrastructure provides for interlinked, FAIR datasets, in experiments with lexical datasets derived from different kinds of sources, such as dictionaries in CSV format (Huaman et al., 2023), Ontolex-Lemon TTL (Lindemann et al., 2023), and, recently, DMLEX (Krek et al., in press).

3 Outlook to further research

In this paper, we have been revisiting the model for lexical entries on Wikibase, and in Wikidata lexemes, the largest collection of lexical data on a Wikibase today, and which is also, probably, the largest Ontolex use case. It can be stated that, by reusing Ontolex-Lemon, the Wikibase software enables the community to perform steps towards the vision of a *Linked Lexical Data Cloud* (Declerck, 2018).

Since the first publications of the Lemon model (McCrae et al., 2012), which had been available by the time of defining the Wikibase Ontology, the Ontolex community has been publishing modeling proposals as modules, regarding, among other aspects, the description of morphology, etymology, and corpus attestations.⁶⁷ In the same timespan and in parallel, there has been emerging a tradition of modeling lexemes on Wikidata. One research question seems obvious in this context: Where and how do both models differ, where do they come together? Where can they benefit from each other? What advantages and disadvantages have the two strategies, compared to each other: A top-down model with strict recommendations, aiming at interoperable lexical datasets also at a more fine-grained level (Ontolex), and a model that limits obligatory interoperability to the core, leaving decisions regarding fine-grained descriptions up to the user (Wikibase), aiming at higher levels of interoperability through on-the-fly grassroots community discussions (Wikidata)? This can shed lights on questions about whether the Lemon

core has proven its functionality, if the obligatory core should be extended, or if even some of the minimum requirements might turn out problematic for certain use cases. Comparing both universes may lead to useful insight: Can the Wikidata lexemes collection provide data-driven evidence for modeling decisions that can be regarded universal, beyond the Ontolex-lemon core? And, in the other direction: Can collaborators or automatic tools informed in Ontolex-Lemon modeling proposals help grassroots communities to improve consistency, quality assessment and interoperability? A continued dialogue between the Ontolex and the Wikidata lexemes communities, and those around other instances of the Wikibase software, will help to address these questions in detail.

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⁶⁵See <https://wikibase.cloud>.

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